

ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (HRM) PRACTICES ON EMPLOYEE JOB PERFORMANCE: A STUDY OF USMANU DANFODIYO UNIVERSITY SOKOTO

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Abstract

The quest to achieve more with less among organizations around the globe is always on the increase. Again, organization commitment towards improving their Human Resource Management (HRM) practices which is believed worldwide to be a sine qua non to attaining efficiency becomes very evident. This study examines the effects of Human Resource Management practices on employees' job performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The study tests the proposition that an effective HRM practices have positive effects on the employees' job performance and the results unraveled that some not all the HRM practices correlates significantly with employee job performance even though all are related. It was however suggested that constant review of the HRM practices for organizations to move with time should be employed.

Keywords: Recruitment, Training, Involvement, Reward, Maintenance, Separation

1. Introduction

Job Performance has become one of the significant indicators in measuring organizational performance in many studies (Wall, Michie, Patterson, Wood, Sheehan, Clegg, & West, 2004). Even though performance is oftentimes determined by financial figures, it can also be measured through the combination of expected behavior and task-related aspects (Motowidlo, 2003). In fact, performance that is based on an absolute value or relative judgment may reflect overall organizational performance (Gomez-Mejia, Balkin, & Cardy, 2007; Wall *et al.*, 2004).

Schmitt and Chan sighted in Motowidlo (2003) categorized Employee Job Performance into 'will-do' and 'can-do'. The former refers to individuals' knowledge, skills, abilities and other characteristics (KSAOs) required in performing certain job and the latter denotes the motivation level that individuals may have in performing their work.

Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart, & Wright (2010) defined Human Resource Management as a philosophy, policy, system and practices that can affect the behavior, attitudes and performance of employees. Activities of HRM include HRM planning, staffing, training and development, performance management, compensation management, safety and health and employee relations. In an early stage, the management of organization has ignored the function of HRM practices as a main driver of organizational success. Only lately, the potential role of HRM in enhancing organization performance has been realized. HRM practices can improve the performance of organizations by contributing to employee and customer satisfaction, innovation, productivity, and development of good reputation among firm's community (Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Noe *et al.*, 2010).

1.2 Issue

Despite the immense importance of Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices towards the realization of Employees Job Performance in particular and organizational performance in general, many organizations do not give emphases to its effective utilization so as to ensure organizational performance in developing countries like Nigeria.

Series of studies have been conducted on Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices in Europe, America, and different parts of Asian continents but little were conducted in Africa in general and Nigeria in particular. Most of those little studies conducted on Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices in Nigeria, focus more on organization strategy in private organizations like banks, manufacturing firms etc with few from public sector organizations (see Anakwe, 2002, Okpu & Emiti 2011). Furthermore, the studies emphasized on the effects or impacts of Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices on organizational performance not employees job performance. These theoretical flaws motivate the researchers on the need for yet another study on the effects of Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices on Employee Job Performance in a public sector organization to be able to bridge the gap.

1.3 Objective of the study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the effects of HRM practices on the employee job performance using Usmanu Danfodiyo University as the study area. Other specific objectives are:

1. To examine the relationship between Recruitment/Selection and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
2. To examine the relationship between Training/development and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.

3. To examine the relationship between Employee Involvement and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
4. To examine the relationship between Reward/Compensation and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
5. To examine the relationship between Maintenance and Employee job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
6. To examine the relationship between Separation and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.

1.4 *Scope of study*

This study covers an assessment of the effects of Human Resource Management practices (Recruitment/Selection, Training and Development, Employee Involvement, Maintenance, Compensation and Rewards, and Separation) on employee job performance with particular reference to Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.

1.5 *Hypotheses*

- 1 There is a significant relationship between Recruitment/Selection and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
2. There is a significant relationship between Training/Development and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
3. There is a significant relationship between Employee Involvement and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
4. There is a significant relationship between Reward/Compensation and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
5. There is a significant relationship between Maintenance and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.
6. There is a significant relationship between Separation and Employee Job Performance in Usmanu Danfodiyo University.

2. Literature review

2.1 *The Concept of HRM*

Initially, Human Resource Management was developed as a US management concept which lays emphasis on the individual worker and the need to treat people as assets rather than cost (Wilkinson 1990; Beaumont 1992). Though it was widely accepted as the new management practice, the concept remains undefined as it is applied in different ways. Guest (1987: 504) identifies three main approaches to HRM: Firstly, HRM as a new title for personnel management, pointing that organizations rename their personnel department without necessarily changing practices, secondly, HRM as a way of re conceptualizing and reorganizing personnel roles and describing the work of personnel department, and thirdly HRM as a totally new approach for management with a distinctiveness which lies in the integration of human resource into strategic management and the emphasis on full and positive utilization of these resources. HRM is therefore defined as:

“A set of policies designed to maximize organizational integration, employee commitment, flexibility and quality of

work. Within this model, collective industrial relations have at best only a minor role” (Guest 1987:503).

Guest’s (1987) definition brings out the individualistic and unitary nature of HRM. In Storey’s (1992) seminal work, it was further highlighted that the unitary aspect of HRM as effective management that reaffirm employees’ commitment to the realization of company goals.

Human Resource Management is the process of getting, training, assessing, and compensating employees, and maintaining labor relations, health and safety, and fairness concerns (Dessler & Varkkey, 2009; 2011a & b). In a related fashion, Mondy *et al.*, (2005) placed that “Human Resource Management is the utilization of individuals to achieve organizational objectives.” Similarly, Noe *et al.*, (2007) argued Human Resource Management refers to the policies, practices, and systems that influence employees’ behavior, attitudes and performance. So it could be said here that HRM is such a process that focuses to get the best output from employees by focusing on the policies, practices, and systems that influence employee performance.

Contrary to the arguments posed by those scholars as sighted in the previous paragraphs, Hendry and Pettigrew (1990), however take a different stance away from the hard verses soft debate arguing that there is need to shift from prescriptivism to descriptive analysis of structures and strategy making processes of organization. They pointed out that, developing the necessary framework for understanding these structures and strategies are essential underpinnings of HRM. Keenoy (1999) in his hologram discourse, dissolves the various conflicting views of HRM by presenting the concept as a “complex holistic process” and to gain deeper understanding one has to factor in the different forms it takes just like a hologram.

Armstrong (2001) gives an all inclusive sum up of the various views of HRM as:

“A strategic and coherent approach to the management of an organization’s most valued assets: the people working there who individually and collectively contribute to the achievement of its objective” (Armstrong 2001:3- 4).

Apart from the unitary view of HRM expressed in the previous paragraph, another central feature of HRM is the decentralization of responsibility to line managers. The general view is that line managers are essential for the effectiveness of HRM practices regardless of the type of or version of the concept in question. Lowe (1992) reaffirms this point adding that line management play a more significant function in the implementation and drive of HRM. Thus, the function of line managers does not only focus on purely technical responsibilities but also play a role in enhancing the human aspect of HRM (see Poole & Jenkins 1997).

2.2 HRM Practices

There is no agreement on what constitutes HRM practices let alone a prescribed set of them, (Boxall, 2007). Researchers have over the years proposed countless varied lists of practices however; there is no agreement on what or which practice qualifies as an aspect of HRM (Beer *et al.*, 1984; Boselie *et al.* 2005; Guest 1997; Storey 1995). It is interesting to note that there are still some practices that form the core of the various practices proposed. These include recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management and reward scheme, however, others such as job design and employee involvement are more sporadic and are yet to gain grounds in the HRM literature. Guest

(1997) however puts forward seven practices namely, selection, training, appraisal, rewards, job design, involvement and status and security. However, the study focuses on six out of the seven practices in its analysis. Selection of the practices for study is based on its recurrence in the literature reviewed, its significance and measurability. The following is a list of the practices and definitions in relation to this study.

i Recruitment/Selection

This involves two interrelated processes, recruitment is the process of generating a pool of capable people to apply for employment to an organization while selection is the process by which specific instruments are employed to choose from a pool of applicants persons most suitable for the job taking into consideration management goals and legal requirements (Bratton & Gold 2003). Armstrong (2001) categorizes recruitment and selection into three stages: defining requirement, attracting candidates and selecting candidates.

The recruitment and selection process is one of the most important HRM functions as it is the point of entry into most organizations and in addition where most organizations recruit talents that drive their goals and interest. It also reflects the requirements and philosophy of the organization as reflected in the caliber of people chosen for the job.

Various techniques are employed in the recruitment and selection process and these include various forms of interviews, assessment centres, curriculum vitae, references amongst others.

ii Training/Development

“Training is the formal and systematic modification of behavior through learning which occurs as a result of education, instruction, development and planned experience”(Armstrong, 2001). Training can be on the job or off the job depending on the need in question. Appropriate training is required for various needs such as: to solve pertinent problems, to boost performance, and also for continuous development of human resource.

The practice is one of the most important aspects of HRM needed to keep organizations ahead of their competitors Hilb (1992). A rigorous study conducted by Koch and Mcgrath (1996) demonstrated that firms that engage in systematic training of their workforce are more likely to enjoy the rewards of a more productive workforce.

iii Employee Involvement

The concept of treating employees as the most important assets of an organization is an underlying assumption of HRM. As such, to facilitate and enhance greater employee influence and involvement is obviously basic to successful HRM practice in organization. Poole and Jenkins (1997) proposed three principle routes to greater employee involvement which includes: Legislated standards on employee participation (example work councils, support for employee financial participation) trade unions for both formal and informal collective bargaining and management initiatives to support employee participation in the work itself and to provide opportunities for employees to voice their views on development and problems (see Beer *et al.*, 1984; Poole & Mansfield, 1993).

iv Reward/Remuneration

The remuneration process is crucial and a source of contention in most organizations. It deals with rewarding people in accordance with their value in the organization. It is concerned with both financial and non financial rewards and embraces the strategies, philosophies plans and processes employed by organizations to develop and maintain reward systems.

An inclusive and effective HRM strategy has a coherent approach to rewards as one of its most central component (Armstrong & Murlis 1991; Poole & Jenkins 1997). It plays a motivational role in management hence the importance attached to it. Pay strategies include performance related pay, production based pay, skill based, knowledge based and base pay (Brown 1989).

v. Maintenance

Maintenance is the administration and monitoring of workplace safety, health and welfare policies to retain a competent workforce and comply with statutory standards and regulations. It is also an organizational activity of Sustaining and improving working conditions, retentions, employee communication etc. Maintenance in organizations is usually achieved through employee's welfare and motivation. So welfare and motivation are used to be able to retained them (employees) and make them be committed to their jobs.

vi. Separation

Separation is defined as an act of strategic approach towards employee development and ensuring continuity by taking positive steps to fill resource gaps caused by resignations, terminations, layoffs, death, medical sickness etc.

2.3 Employee Job Performance

Employee Job performance has been a concern for organizations and researchers. For decades, researchers have been looking for different ways to enhance Employee Job Performance. Job performance refers to “behaviors or actions that are relevant to the goals of the organization in question” (McCloy, Campbell, & Cudeck, 1994). Performance is a multi dimensional variable in which every job has distinct performance components (McCloy *et al.*, 1994). Porter and Lawler (1968) argued that attitudes influence performance. For example, Christen, *et al.* (2006), Cohrs, *et al.* (2006), Rayton (2006), and Zhang and Zheng (2009) found evidence that job satisfaction – an attitudinal variable – influences job performance – a behavioral variable. In their empirical study, Lawler and Porter (1967) reported that “satisfaction of higher order needs would be the most closely related to performance”. Although the causal direction between job satisfaction and job performance is still not resolved, Judge, Thoresen, Bono and Patton (2001) found that the average true correlation between job satisfaction and job performance was estimated to be 0.30.

2.4 HRM Practices and Employee Job Performance

Early studies linked individual HRM practices such as training, selection, performance appraisal and compensation to firm financial performance (Milkovich, 1992; Huselid, 1995; Guest, 1997). Research has led to the identification of a number of Human Resource Management practices that contribute to performance across different organizations (Huselid, 1995). In a literature review, Delery & Doty (1996) identified seven such practices that have been consistently considered HRM practices. They defined HRM practices as those that are theoretically or empirically related to overall organizational performance. These practices include internal career opportunities, formal training systems, results-oriented appraisals, employment security, participation, job descriptions, and profit sharing.

The relationship between Human Resource practices and work out comes is an increasingly researched topic in human resource management (e.g. Edgar & Geare, 2005; Truss, Gratton, Hope-Hailey, McGovern & Stiles, 1997). More specifically, HRM is hypothesized to fulfill employees' needs which enhances favorable attitudes, and subsequently improves performance outcomes (Edgar & Geare, 2005; Kuvaas, 2008; Meyer & Allen, 1997). This is

consistent with social exchange theory (SET) which argues that HRM practices contribute to positive exchange relationships between employee and employer – especially when the needs of individual workers are considered – to which employees reciprocate with favorable attitudes and behavior (Gould-Williams & Davies, 2005).

Luna-Arocas and Camps (2008) found HRM practices such as training, empowerment, rewards, job enrichment, and job stability to affect turnover intention through job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Similarly, Saks, and Rotman (2006) found that while job characteristics such as autonomy and feedback foster work engagement, a higher level of work engagement subsequently lowers employees’ intention to quit.

Previous studies have also shown that implementing HRM practices is an important means through which favorable outcomes can be fostered. For example, the presence of strong recruitment and selection practices, promotional opportunities, grievance resolution mechanisms, flexible benefit plans, employee responsibility, autonomy, and team work were found to relate positively to organizational commitment while compensation cuts were negatively associated with organizational commitment (Caldwell, Chatman & O’Reilly, 1990; Fiorito, Bozeman, Young & Meurs, 2007; Gould-Williams & Davies, 2005; Heshizer, 1994). In addition, satisfaction with and perceived adequacy of career development, training opportunities, and performance appraisal were established as predictors of organizational commitment (Kuvaas, 2008). Research Framework was depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Framework

3. Research Methodology

This paper focuses on descriptive and causal research (hypotheses testing) since it is aimed at explaining the relationship between the variables with a cross-sectional survey design using a sample of 285 teaching staff from a population of 1027 academic staffs of Usmanu Danfodiyo university Sokoto. A regression analysis was run and a multicollinearity test was also conducted. Out of the 285 sample (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970), only 198 provided the needed information related to the topic selected, the analysis however was based on the 198 respondents. A single instrument was used for data collection which was designed on 5-point Likert scales to measure the various variables. A content and construct analysis was undertaken by making use of extensive literature and previously validated constructs.

4. Data Presentation and Analyses

The data collected was keyed into SPSS and the result of the study was analyzed on the basis of descriptive statistics, correlations and regressions analyses.

Table 1
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.663 ^a	.440	.429		.7565354

a. Predictors: (Constant), RCT, TRN, INV, RWD, MNT, SEP

Table 1: above indicates that the regression equation was significant, $R = .663$, $R^2 = .440$, R^2 adjusted = .429. In other words, the multiple correlation coefficients between the independent and the dependent variable were .663; the independent variable accounted for 44% of the variance in the employee job performance.

Table 2
Multi Co linearity Test

Model		Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Co linearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.000	.042		.000	1.000		
	RCT	.340	.052	.340	6.567	.000	.666	1.501
	TRN	.070	.052	.070	1.360	.175	.666	1.500
	INV	.167	.056	.167	3.006	.003	.579	1.728
	RWD	.114	.056	.114	2.033	.043	.564	1.772
	MNT	.188	.063	.188	2.973	.003	.445	2.249
	SEP	-.026	.064	-.026	-.403	.687	.434	2.302

Table 2 above displays the results of the multi-co linearity test and shows that there is no problem of multi-co linearity because the co linearity tolerance values turned out to be greater than 0.2 and the VIF statistics are all less than 5, (rule of thumb), i.e. RCT has tolerance value of .666 and VIF statistics = 1.501; TRN possesses a tolerance figure of .666 and VIF statistics of 1.500; INV has a tolerance value of .579 with a corresponding VIF value of 1.728; RWD has a tolerance value of .564 and a VIF statistic figure of 1.772; MNT and SEP also have tolerance value of .445 and .434 with corresponding VIF statistic values of 2.249 and 2.302 respectively.

Table 3
Correlations

		EJP	RCT	TRN	INV	RWD	MNT	SEP
EJP	Pearson Correlation	1	.567	.407	.497	.457	.506	.448
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	198	198	198	198	198	198	198
RCT	Pearson Correlation	.567	1	.434	.448	.406	.466	.472
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	198	198	198	198	198	198	198
TRN	Pearson Correlation	.407	.434	1	.439	.493	.373	.414
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	198	198	198	198	198	198	198
INV	Pearson Correlation	.497	.448	.439	1	.512	.545	.533
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	198	198	198	198	198	198	198
RWD	Pearson Correlation	.457	.406	.493	.512	1	.525	.551
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	198	198	198	198	198	198	198
MNT	Pearson Correlation	.506	.466	.373	.545	.525	1	.703
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	198	198	198	198	198	198	198
SEP	Pearson Correlation	.448	.472	.414	.533	.551	.703	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	198	198	198	198	198	198	198

Table 3 above displays the correlations among variables, and the results revealed that the entire variables are significantly correlated at 2 tailed.

Table 4
Results of hypotheses testing

Hypotheses	Original Sample (O)	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	Results
RCT -> EJP	0.34	0.14	1.24	0.23	YES
TRN -> EJP	0.11	0.09	1.26	0.21	YES
INV -> EJP	0.17	0.14	1.24	0.22	YES
RWD -> EJP	0.07	0.13	0.51	0.9	NO
MNT -> EJP	0.19	0.15	1.23	0.22	YES
SEP -> EJP	0.19	0.16	1.22	0.22	YES

The results of the test in table 4 above indicate that all but one of the six hypothesized statements were proven and supported as alternative hypotheses. This is reflected in the results obtained. Thus, H1 (**RCT -> EJP**) is supported because, the β value = 0.34, t-value = 1.24, and a P value of 0.23. The second hypothesis H2 (**TRN -> EJP**) is also proven as alternative because of what was evident in the β value = 0.11, t-value = 1.26, and a P value = 0.21. Hypothesis H3 (**INV -> EJP**) was supported; it has a β value of 0.17, a t-value of 1.24 and a p-value of 0.22. The fourth hypothesis H4 (**RWD -> EJP**) was not supported as a result of the fact that β value = 0.07, t-value = 0.51 and a p-value of 0.9. The fifth hypothesis H5 (**MNT -> EJP**) was also supported; it has a β value of 0.19, a t-value of 1.23 and a p-value of 0.22. Hypothesis H6 was as well supported as shown in the β value = 0.19, t-value = 1.22 and a p-value = 0.22. The hypotheses were supported and / or not supported based on their respective p-values. If the p-value is less than 0.5 the hypotheses is supported and if it goes beyond 0.5, it is not supported (rule of thumb).

5 Conclusion

It is concluded that the HRM practices in Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto are very much related to the Employee Job Performance as the results of the test in table 4 indicated that all five out of the six human resource (HRM) practices and activities showed significant influence and impact on the employee job performance and the only exception was reward. This finding on the relationship between HRM practices and employees job performance is established by the strategic HRM researches. HRM manages the organization's human assets and resources. Effective HRM enables the university employees to contribute productively and effectively for the achievement of the organization's objectives and goals.

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